

β -2-Pyridyl-resorcinolsuccinein as Adsorption Indicator in the Argentometric Titrations

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A new substituted succinein i.e., β -2-pyridyl-resorcinolsuccinein (I) was prepared for use as an adsorption indicator in the argentometric titrations of halides and thiocyanate, and it has been found that (I) is in many respects better than the well known fluorescein dye¹⁻³.

Material used. NaCl, KBr, KI, and AgNO₃ were A.R. (BDH) and KSCN was L.R. (BDH) grade reagents.

Indicators solution. A 0.1% solution of the dye (I) was prepared in rectified spirit. 3-6 drops of the indicator (depending on the concentration of the solution) were used for every 10 ml of the solution titrated.

Preparation of the dye. β -2-pyridoylpropionic acid was condensed with resorcinol in presence of a few drops of conc. H₂SO₄. The condensed mass was crushed, washed with water and extracted with 2% NaOH solution. The pinkish-red extraction was precipitated by the gradual addition of dil. HCl; it was recrystallised from rectified spirit by the gradual and cautious addition of cold distilled water till the turbidity appeared. The crystallised dye was dried in an oven at 110°. The dye melting at 200° showed all the properties of the fluorescein dye, and was used as adsorption indicator.

The adsorption properties of the dye (I) and its comparison with fluorescein are as given under :

β -2-pyridyl-resorcinolsuccinein (I). Titrations are possible for Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and SCN⁻.

Suspension or solution with 0.1-0.005N NaCl solutions (pink tinged-white, pinkish-white, light pink) → bright pink ppt.

Note : With 0.004N solution, the end point colour change is quite recognisable (from pink tinged-white → light pink) but no coagulation takes place.

Fluorescein as an adsorption indicator, can be used well up to 0.01N dilution.

Suspension or solution with 0.1-0.005N KBr solutions (orange tinged-yellow, light orange-pink, light orange) → bright pink ppt.

Note : With 0.004N solution, 5-6 min shaking is required for the coagulation of the orange-pink ppt.

Fluorescein does not give sharp end points beyond 0.01N dilution.

Suspension or solution with 0.1-0.0025N KI solutions (orange-yellow, light orange, yellow) → bright pink ppt.

Note : With 0.002-0.00125N solutions, the end point colour change is sharp (from light orange solution → light pink) but no coagulation takes place.

Fluorescein cannot be used well beyond 0.01N dilution.

Suspension or solution with 0.1-0.01N KSCN solutions (pinkish-white, orange tinged-white, light orange-pink) → bright pink ppt.

Note : With 0.005-0.0025N solutions, the end point colour change (from light orange solution → pink) is quite recognisable, but the coagulation of the pink ppt. starts taking place after shaking the solutions for 3-5 min at the end point.

Fluorescein can be used up to 0.01N dilution with much shaking at the end point.

Fluorescein. Well known for the titration of halides and thiocyanate ions. Yellow suspension (Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and SCN⁻) → bright pink ppt.

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A Method for Detection of Diterpene Ingenol by GLC

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IN continuation of our study on the distribution of the cocarcinogenic substances among the plants of Euphorbiaceae¹, it was noted that the irritant and tumor promoting activity on mice back skin of the latex samples is mainly due to the presence of the fatty acid esters of diterpene ingenol^{2,3}. In the present communication a detection method of ingenol, which is present in the latex samples and in the total plant extract, in very small amounts, is described. Ingenol containing fraction was acetylated and the crude 3, 5, 20 tri-acetate in some cases was purified by TLC: C₂₆H₃₄O₈(MS), parent ion: m/e 474, UV (MeOH) λ_{max} : 212, 292; ϵ = 16,300, 220, IR (CH₂Cl₂): 1740, 1705, 1640 cm⁻¹, R_f = 0.75 (hexane, ethyl acetate, ether, 1 : 1 : 1)⁴ and in most of the times was injected directly, with the internal reference codeine (methanolic solution : 0.05% W/V) in Varian Aerograph model-1400 equipped with flame ionising detector. The column and detector temperatures were kept on 210° and 230° respectively. The irritation assay (IU, ID₅₀) in case of the latex samples was done following the standard method⁵, where as with the total plant extract the assay was performed by dissolving a small amount of the water free methanolic extract in acetone and then following the standard method⁶.

Ingenol has been detected from the latex samples and from the plant extracts using SE-30 and 5% QF₁ columns. Table I contains the irritation dose 50, relative retention time and other details. It has been further noted that 5% QF₁ column is better as

NOTES

TABLE 1— R_{RT} AND ID_{60} OF VARIOUS SAMPLES OF EUPHORBIA INVESTIGATED CONTAINING TERPENE INGENOL

Euphorbia species	ID_{60} $\mu\text{g}/\text{ear}$		Relative retention time on	
	Latex	Plant extract	Column 1	Column 2
<i>E. serrata</i>	1.5	> 100	2.63	3.8
<i>E. seguieriana</i>	1.1	> 100	2.60	3.8
<i>E. marshalliana</i>	—	—	2.59	3.8
<i>E. esula</i>	0.47	> 100	2.61	3.7
<i>E. virgata</i>	0.30	> 100	2.60	3.8

Column 1 : SE-30, 100/120 mesh, on varaport 30 : Nitrogen flow rate : 60 ml/min, Hydrogen flow rate : 30 ml/min, Codeine retention time : 21 min.

Column 2 : 5% QF₁, 60/80 mesh, Chrom.W. Nitrogen-flow rate : 62 ml/min, Hydrogen flow rate as in case of column 1, Codeine retention time : 12 min

compared to SE-30 column, because it gives quick result. Applying this combination it is possible to

know if the tumor promoting and irritant activity associated with the latex samples or with the total plant extracts, is because of ingenol or due to some other substances.

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